

EXPLORING THE CONFLICT TRANSFORMATION PROCESSES TOWARDS PEACE IN COTABATO PROVINCE: A PHENOMENOLOGICAL STUDY

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ABSTRACT

Conflict transformation necessitates identifying causes of conflict and collaborative actors for the development of peace. A phenomenological research study was conducted to explore the transformational processes in three conflicted areas in Cotabato province in terms of peacebuilding, economic, and security. A self-made guided questionnaire through individual interview and focus group discussions (FGD) was used. For thematic analysis, a descriptive core codes were generated and translated into English. These codes were grouped and tabled according to their similarity and relevance to the research questions. Captured themes were generated after analyzing the relationship of core ideas to the questions. Results found that the restoration of peace reflects eliminating prejudice, building strong support systems, and welcoming cultural boundaries. In addition, upholding culture-to-culture, and people-to-people relations forge genuine peace for all.

Keywords: *Conflict transformation processes, peacebuilding process, economic process, security process, peace, Cotabato Province*

INTRODUCTION

Due to various prolonged conflicts (Åkebo, 2020) ranging from Moro to communist insurgent forces, the Southern part of Mindanao has been dubbed the land of animosity and terror for the past four decades (Ballesteros, 2020; Loesch, 2017a). People are

reluctant to go out and engage in economic activities because safety has become intangible. According to Ochiai (2016), there were three key explanations why the Mindanao conflicts had lasted so long: inequalities and injustices, ancestral domain, and political and economic depression. Conflicts continued to claim thousands of lives and wealth, but not until the new Bangsamoro government was formed, led by the Moro Islamic Liberation Front (MILF), to foster peace and honor their heritage (Ochiai, 2016).

The peace deal in 2014 between the MILF and GRP formally ends long runny war and paved the way to improve people-to-people and culture-to-culture relationships. The peace deals serve as a parameter to stop military and violent coercion and provide dynamic opportunities for development. Conflict transformation in this case has become an emerging social and political aspect that helps to provide a clear path towards peace. However, few studies have been conducted on conflict transformation processes.

Therefore, this study aims to explore the processes involved in the achievement of peace in Cotabato province particularly in the context of peacebuilding, economic and security. By exploring the different processes, this study identifies the elements that allow in the transformation of the locality that once called conflict-affected areas to more peaceful.

Research Questions

This study generally aimed to explore the processes from conflict to peace in conflict-affected areas in Cotabato province. Moreover, it tried to answer the following questions.

1. What were the explored processes of transition from conflict to peace in terms of:
 - A. Peacebuilding processes of transition from conflict to peace
 - a.1 What are their beliefs towards peace?
 - a.2 Who are the people or sectors involved in the process of transformation?
 - a.3 What multi-sectorial initiatives are taken toward peace?
 - a.4. What are problems encountered in the process of transformation.
 - a.5 What perceived effect of transition processes to peace development of the peaceful situation in the said localities (both long term and short term) to the localities.
 - B. Economic processes of transition from conflict to peace
 - b.1 How can peace be achieved through economic processes?
 - b.2 What is the economic situation of the people during the time of conflict?
 - b.3 What economic activities/strategies are done to cope with conflicts situations?
 - b.4.What are the interventions applied to economic situation (stable income, increase income, alternative income sources) during the time of conflict?
 - b.5 What are perceived effects of interventions during the time of conflict?
 - C. Security processes of transition from conflict to peace?

- c. 1. Who/ what sectors usually destabilize security in the area?
- c. 2. Who are the people tasked to maintain security?
- c. 3. What activities are done to maintain security?
- c. 4. How did the community participate in maintaining security?
- c. 5. What are the problems encountered in maintaining security?
- c. 6. What are perceived effects of interventions during that time?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study employed a phenomenological research design. Using this method, the researcher was able to qualify the underlying narratives of the participants' context, personal experiences, and perceptions about conflict and peace transitions. According to Creswell & Creswell (2018), using this method describes and culminates the essence of the experiences of several individuals who have all experienced the phenomenon. In addition, these narratives captured prevailing concerns and guide conceptualizing themes and descriptions to answer the research questions.

Participants

The following parameters were used in the selection process. There were participants coming from the municipalities of Aleosan, Pikit, and Makilala. For the Key Informant Interview (KII), six participants were interviewed comprising the LGU Tourism Officer and BLGU Barangay Captain. They currently hold the office and have the knowledge about current tourism development and living in time of conflict. For the Focus Group Discussion (FGD), eighteen participants were interviewed including the owners of the tourist site, head of BPAT, teacher, vendor, habal-habal drivers and Brgy. Kagawad. As to their inclusion, they should be a resident of the barangay, living at the time of conflict and have some knowledge about peace integration in their area.

Setting

This research took place in the province of Cotabato, which is part of Region XII, also known as the SOCCSKARGEN region. The province's total land area, including urban and rural areas, is 9,008.90 square kilometers. According to the most recent Regional Department of Tourism XII survey conducted in March 2021, the Cotabato province reported 216 182 tourists, both domestic and foreign. In addition, some local attractions in the province can be found in nearby neighboring municipalities of Aleosan, Pikit, and Makilala, which have been identified as research participants. These areas were identified prior to the inclusion in the geographical area of BARMM.

Aleosan has a total land area of 225.44 square kilometers, accounting for 2.42 percent of the province's total land area. According to the 2020 Census, the municipality had 41 944 people spread across 19 barangays. The U.K. Peak, located in the barangays of Upper

Mingading and Katalicanan, is a thriving tourist attraction. In comparison, the Municipality of Pikit has a total land area of 604.61 square kilometers, or 6.49 percent of the total land area of Cotabato. It had a total population of 164,646 people, according to the 2020 Census. The historical Fort Pikit, built during the Spanish military regime in 1893, is a tourist attraction that the municipality can be proud. It is located near the municipal hall along the national highway. The municipality of Makilala, endowed with natural resources, is one of the tourist attractions. In comparison, the Municipality of Pikit has a total land area of 604.61 square kilometers, or 6.49 percent of the total land area of Cotabato. It had a total population of 164,646 people, according to the 2020 Census. The historical Fort Pikit, built during the Spanish military regime in 1893, is a tourist attraction that the municipality can be proud. It is located near the municipal hall along the national highway. The municipality of Makilala, endowed with natural resources, is one of the province's most popular tourist destinations. The New Israel Eco-tourism Park, located in Barangay Israel, has become an obvious attraction to local and foreign visitors. There is a fun adventure that includes a zip line and a scenic view of Mt. Apo during the visit. It covers 343, 57 square kilometers of land, accounting for 3.69 percent of Cotabato's total land area. According to the 2020 Census, the municipality has 87,927 people.

Instruments

The study's instruments used a researcher-made interview guide. Before proceeding to actual data collection, the research tool was subject to validation by researchers. Also, a pilot test was conducted to determine the suitability and accuracy of the questions and probes. The Key Informant Interview (KII) and Focus Group Discussion (FGD) guide questionnaire used the same questions to vouch their responses.

Data Analysis

The obtained information from the interview with the participants during KII and FGD was transcribed verbatim. An inductive approach was used in filtering important responses. The researcher did descriptive coding out of the individual and group responses using the probing questions as a guide. Descriptive core codes were generated and translated into English. These codes were grouped and tabled according to their similarity and relevance to the research questions. Captured themes were generated after analyzing the relationship of core ideas to the questions.

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RESULTS

This section provided responses of the participants on how the LGU, government agencies, and stakeholders come up with localized solutions in conflict-affected areas. These conflict transformation processes towards peace aimed to unfold intervention infused by stakeholders. These exploration processes were anchored to peacebuilding, economic, and security.

A. Peacebuilding Process of Transition from Conflict to Peace

A1. Peace Perspectives

The peacebuilding process comes across the views of the participants in dealing with peace. Because of the marginalizing effect of conflict, the community loudly seeks hope to attain peace. The community had continued to amplify their peaceful perspective that at the end of the day, they could now build better homes and live harmoniously. Common to peace perspectives were themes like presence of economic stability, development, orderly life, communal security, and predisposed goodness.

Table 1: Peace Perspectives

Themes	Description
Economic Stability	Jobs, business, and food opportunities are present. Mushrooming livelihood activities
Development	Community keeps on growing

Orderly life	People can plan out their lives. Living a good life. Living without fear. Being able to sleep properly. Clarity of mind. Freedom to walk.
Communal Security	There is no disturbance. Peace in the neighborhood. Harmonious relationship and unity between Christians and Muslims. Absence of threats, conflict, or war. Normal activities in the community.
Predisposed to goodness	Doing no harm to others.

Economic stability

Economic stability prospered because of this relevant sustenance in terms of livelihood were operated in the event where conflict was visible to their locality. Through peacebuilding efforts of stakeholders, NGOs and LGUs, the community itself experiences a tremendous healing where they can find solitude in time of crisis. There were more opportunities provided, voluntary aid and relief were administered. Satisfactory responses can be seen in the smile of the community.

Development

Another evidence of peace perspective is development. Due to an increase of support from the locality and community, the presence of business, infrastructure, affiliations to different agencies for partnership makes relevant development. By this, the community was moving into positive development where the presence of growth and coming in of investment become visible in the area. The way the community defined development is that farming is not only the resource that they can depend on but also able to have additional income. The participants observed that they feel confident to live in their community. Unlike before, the uncertainties were the reasons for losing hope and aspirations to grow.

Orderly life

By this, they considered that upon the intervention of agencies and stakeholders to address the issues of conflict, they were saying that it looked like it is an orderly life again. The restoration of peace expressed a vantage to live a life full of order. This signified that they never more worried to sleep at night, nothing to think whether anytime they will vacate their homes. They can now freely move and go in the market and public spaces without hesitation if there are bomb threats and or even killings. For the participants, peaceful life is orderly life.

Communal Security

The community observed in the process of transition that communal security remained active. Security forces tangled localities and communities by promoting immediate response to disputes. The concern for peace and security is not limited to one municipality

but also observed in other areas. As a result of cooperation and strategic partnership, it gave birth to conflict emancipation. This commitment to peace promotes community stability by encouraging men to promote justice, harmonious relationships, and a secure environment in which they can continue their advocacy for the promotion of security.

Predisposed to goodness.

The way peace enshrined by the participants’ responses was the predisposition to goodness. By this, restorations become vital on how it will be grounded into mutual dream of the community, now a living reality. Everything must be put to order where the desirable aim is to let everyone experiencing happy life, secured environment, and absence of war. After decades of misunderstanding and threats to their area, the community wanted to end it because it did not help them to achieve their plans in life. It disturbed their plans. The community wanted to let go of this conflict and move to desirable ends where it formed community’s solidarity. Other participants highlighted their effort to end the conflict.

A2. Sectoral Initiatives in the Process

These sectoral initiatives developed support to the community namely the national government, provincial government, LGU, BLGU, OPAG, DSWD, DA, DepEd, DoT, Engineering department, Congressman’s Office, SK, NGOs, and Business sectors.

Table 2: Sectoral Initiatives in the Process

Themes	Description
National Government	The locality seek supports to maintain peace to the conflicted areas
Provincial Government	Funding for the security force.
Local Government Unit	CAFGU, PNP, negotiations. Opening the door for Moro leaders to be part of development planning. Dispersal program. Seeds planting.
Barangay Local Government Unit	Barangay Capt., BPAT. Routinary visitation and purok dialogues. Cooperative Development Plan by the Brgy. Captains. Active Police and BPAT security force. Livelihood such as skills training for weaving, fish drying, and tailoring. Provision of basic needs such as shelter, food, and water pumps. Ramadhan Camps. Capacity building programs for Brgy. Officials. Meeting and coordination between NPA and the barangay. Community orientation and updating.
Office of the Provincial Agriculture	Intervene aid, programs, and training to the community. Coordinate local official base on the needs.
Department of Social Welfare and Development	4Ps, Out of School Youth education, sports festival, and psychosocial intervention.

Department of Agriculture	Augmentation of DA and BFAR to provide livelihood. Techno-demo farm to community. Farmers' exposure to farms of other communities. Benchmarking of best farming practices.
Department of Education	Teachers, Alternative Learning System (ALS)
Department of Tourism	Tourism investment. Tourism as a "means" to achieve peace. Pooled funds for fish port and fishing boats, housing, and dryer for women. Promotion of local products as source of income through tourism.
Engineering Department	Coordinate with community and DoT for road construction and establishment
Congressman's Office	Donated support to water and electricity to the locality
Sangguniang Pangkabataan	The barangay and community invited the young to cooperate and join the programs
Non-Government Organizations	Balay Mindanao, Balay Rehab, Unipad, G7. Tree planting activities.
Business Sectors	Establishment of Cooperatives.

National Government

GRP provided enough military forces to protect areas inhabited by the armed groups. In Barangay New Israel, for an instance, called for reinforcement of CAFGU and AFP in their community. The presence of NPA collapsed the social and economic development. The community were afraid of going to the market. They suspected that they would be ambushed. Incident, threats, and ambush led them to call for GRP to rescue them from prevailing problem. When the arrival of armed forces happened, it showed a big change to the community's environment. They had the feeling of safety. To maintain this, they required the battalion leader if they could build their brigade within their community as they will sure that nothing will happen to them. The manifestation of BPAT was fully organized even though there were CAFGU and AFP around them. Due to the continued support of the GRP to the locality and mainstreaming of community-based voluntourism, the community had the assurance of claiming their place was now free from NPA's threats. The GRP assigned these forces to eradicate fears to the community. As part of their initiative, the CAFGU and AFP continued to supervise their areas by posting guards and headquarters in the vicinity to intensify their security. While the community itself broadens their advocacy through church leaders and local officials to monitor the entrance of visitors going in and out to their barangay.

Provincial Government

The provincial government also responded to the BLGU offices as they adhered to maintain the community's welfare and development. Through the effort of provincial government, the other military men were instructed to provide monitoring, security, and contacts to the community in case of emergency. Recent support in the form of initiatives dealt with economic recovery and training for economic support. The DA and DoT under

the provincial office were primarily tasked to revitalize the seeking needs of the community and to cope with undesirable conflicts.

Local Government Unit

The participants identified different initiatives provided by LGU to the conflicted community. These were implementing security measures, assessing the daily and continues supply of food and medicine. The role can any LGU office was provide an immediate response as necessary to conflicted areas. It can also be considered that they actively immersed to remote places and offer services. In Aleosan for instance, the LGU through DA, DSWD, MPS, and DOE worked as backbone of the office because of their practical assistance to situation where people and security become a challenging situation. The production, distribution, and maintenance were shouldered to these departments. The municipal mayor got to collaborate with barangay captains to respond in reported incidents and offered intervention. In case of existing Rido in Pikit, the mayor went to the villages and officiated mediation not to escalate again. This was to stop prevailing killings and gunfire due to Rido. This amicable effort led to minimizing the occurrences of conflict and leaving acceptance and peaceful conversation with the group leaders.

Barangay Local Government Unit

The community leaders headed by Barangay captains were able to impose a local-based initiative by encouraging the community to be vigilant and refused to entertain any group that had bad intentions. The BLGU took more jobs to settle because in recent scenarios, the conspiracy of revolution (NPA) was happening within their areas. As an alternative strategy, the Barangay officials conducted visitation to the purok leaders and met with the residents to gather information and problems related to conflict.

Office of the Provincial Agriculture

The Office of the Provincial Agriculturist made a greater impact to the locality in contributing to economic and livelihood upliftment. For so long that the effect of conflicts disabled the development, the sharing of agricultural resources brought new life to the farmers to cultivate their abandoned lands for many years. To increase their potential through knowledge delivery, training was given. This was to mediate gaps and lapses in the social and economic aspects of the locality.

Department of Social Welfare and Development

The Department of Social Welfare and Development assisted traumatic incidents and later aid services to the community. According to the participants, intervention programs initiated by the said department showed positive results in normalizing the socio-economic needs of the community. Various programs in the form of 4Ps, Out of School Youth education, and psychological intervention especially those who suffered from intense scenario of fighting and victims of existing conflicts become recipients.

Department of Agriculture

The Department of Agriculture concentrated on livelihood and farming technology considering that main source of come relied from farming. There was ample land for farming and was left unused before since the occurrence of conflict found it disturbing to the locale residents. This intervention of DA with collaboration with LGU hand over livelihood and farming machinery as they will use it as their initial source of income.

Department of Education

The Department of Education had witnessed the difficult challenge to the number of enrollees and attendance of students who were living in conflicted areas. It was noticeable that in the record, the number of dropped out ballooned in time of conflict. These were caused by evacuation and unsafe to travel. Children were forced to move with their parents. They spent much of their time farming and transfer to peaceful barangay. Every time that conflict booms, they will move from one place to another until such time that they lose their focus to study.

Department of Tourism

The Department of Tourism offered economical income through tourism industry as the new trend in the economic development. By this, the participants never imagined that, for decades of unending war and conflict, the LGU could offer the tourist a relaxing tourist spot and promotion of peaceful areas where they could find peace.

Local Engineering Department

The proper coordination between DoT and engineering department forged vital upgrading of local roads that experienced inaccessibility to market. It was considered that uneven road caused time consuming to the residents in travelling to market. At the time when peace agreement was realized, the uprising of tourism industry to municipality became the source of profit of LGU and the community. The concreting of roads connected to tourist spots sprout good ends not only to the LGU and private owners but also to the community who enjoyed the privilege to use it. The participants were able to work efficiently when going to other villages, even the local leaders in assuming their responsibility to them.

Congressman's Office

The office of congressman offered support to the residents in improving their quality of life in terms of water and electricity supply. While the emergence of tourists in their area, the community living within, as in the case of New Israel, had something to improve. For them, sponsored support for a good water supply can be a good sign of collaborative and efficient delivery of services by the government. In the case of Aleosan, the participants also said how the office had provided them with a water supply.

Sangguniang Pangkabataan

The Sangguniang Pangkabataan responded to the needs of their community by organizing themselves as civil individuals and refraining from violent activities. It can be remembered that there were instances in which recruitment to NPA activists' organizations was illusive nearby. To avoid this incident, local leaders called for unified meetings to address the possibility of recruitment. Youth were the most vulnerable and could be easily inspired to join.

Non-Government Organizations

The Non-Government Organizations have become vocal to facilitate and offer comprehensible aid for decades in identified areas. In Pikit for instance, the Balay Mindanao, Unipad, and Balay rehab had consistent benefactors of the barangay. Materials and training were common to these supports. The participants believed that any means of aid they received because of their undying service and programs in their barangay.

Business Sectors

Relative to the coming in of investors and programs of LGUs and NGOs, the participants were able to source opportunities, such as livelihood and small-scale entrepreneurial ownership. Consequently, business opportunities have improved. Hence, additional infrastructure-related businesses have become more frequent in the local area. There were recorded meetings and processes from the identified business sectors that found more opportunities to develop. Proper coordination with LGUs and community were on the lists and target to commence agreement and inauguration of projects. At tourism sites, the community started to engage in small-scale entrepreneurial activities. As the increase in visitors to the area became visible, foods and other locally made products were observable. There were also households that sold their native products along the highway while passengers traveled nearby.

A3. Problems Encountered in the Process of Transformation

In lieu of development during the process of transition, one common scenario that hindered the realizability of government and stakeholders' programs was the problem that arose. Some problems encountered during the process of transition were enumerated by the participants as follows: non-responsive, negative views about conflict, lengthy process of development, inequality, threats, and none. It was not a protest of dismay but a normal activity in progress faced by individuals and agents of the transition process.

Table 3: Problems Encountered in the Process of Transformation

Themes	Description
Non-responsiveness	Non-responsiveness of Moro leaders to intervention plan. Some youth did not want to join. Some women opted to stay at home and not participate. Lack of participation of the community.
Negative views about conflict	Fear that conflict may break in any moment.
Lengthy process of development	Process of development is very long.
Inequality	Unequal delivery of livelihood programs.
Threats	Threats to the citizens occur.

Non-responsiveness

The non-responsiveness of some individuals to the programs and communication, the LGU found difficulty to encourage the community to be part of the programs and initiatives of the government. In Pikit, for instance, it feared that this brought chaos and less opportunities to them.

Negative views about conflict

By this, the participants found more frustrating by tagging their area as an unsafe municipality around the country. It is, however, undeniable that the presence of conflicts caused by series of killings, murder, kidnapping, and war continued to claim lives and development. The residents were also facing discrimination about their place and so, many will not converse with them or even call them tourists.

Lengthy process of development

The development process is tedious. Most people in conflicted areas viewed this as a nearly stagnant process, particularly in terms of economic, social, and physical development. People cannot see any changes or improvements in their way of life. Without prompt actions from authorities, societal problems persist.

Inequality

It occurred when there was a disparity in the distribution of programs that provide livelihood. It was distinguished by social inequalities that manifest themselves within the context of the community. When compared to other members of the community, certain people in the community did not receive the same level of attention. The fundamental problems stemmed from social biases and prejudices, as well as poor program administration and dishonest public officials. Individuals with links to a higher authority,

for instance, receive greater amounts of aid, such as relief supplies, whereas those without such connections must rely on chance.

Threats

This was characterized by various factors and took numerous forms. It was an intent to do harm or act violently against someone or a whole community. With this, chaos is created. Moreover, it causes casualties, inflict trauma, injuries, and economic crisis. Emotionally, the people are under constant strain, and their families live in fear. Some are lamenting the death of family members as combat casualties.

A4. Perceived Effects of Transition Process to Development of Peace

There were generated effects of the development of peace namely the economic determinism, development opportunities, infrastructural improvement, social upliftment. improved quality of life, reversed impression on locality's situation, agricultural development, enhanced government structure, and enhanced government structure.

Table 4: Perceived Effects of Transition Process to Development of Peace

Themes	Description
Economic determinism	Autonomy of the locality to engage in entrepreneurial activities. Livelihood continued; people continued doing business. More visitors patronized local products. Opportunities for better jobs.
Tourism opportunities	Aleosan is open for tourism activities. Increased number of beneficiaries of tourism activities.
Development opportunities	Open doors for realistic development of the people. More livelihood programs were initiated.
Infrastructural improvement	Improved infrastructure, to include barangay and tourism sites. Newly concreted roads.
Social upliftment	Increased youth participation in sports and related programs resulting in relief from trauma. Harmonious living among people. Residents returned to the community for confidence in the locality's safety. Establishment of permanent homes and increase in the number of residents. Efficient communication in the community.
Improved quality of life	Improved lifestyle. Fear is no longer hindering people's mobility. People can now live and enjoy life with family.

Reversed impression on locality's situation	The negative impression on the locality's peace and order situation is reversed. Barangay's image was changed.
Agricultural development	Farmers' activities were created.
Enhanced government structure	Development of barangay head organization. Organized and cooperative government officials.
Enhanced peaceful negotiations	Forged peaceful agreement between the Brgy. Captain and NPA
Absence of Conflict	There is a smooth transition from conflict to peace. There is smooth delivery of programs to the community.

Economic determinism

The government supports and safeguards the citizens' means of subsistence. As a result, individuals feel secure engaging in business activity. Training is provided to guarantee that the populace has the proper business management knowledge, and if they wish to pursue business, they are supported and guided by the government. An increasing number of tourists are beginning to purchase local goods and patronize other local businesses.

Tourism opportunities

Tourism is given top priority, the conflict-affected localities maximize their tourism potential. In which they generate income through the utilization of their natural scenery and other possible tourist attractions. The UK Peak in Aleosan, Bahay Kastila in Pikit, and New Israel in Makilala are examples of these tourist sites. Such attractions are highlighted, and the tourists' protection and safety are guaranteed. This would result in several opportunities, mainly commercial and investment ones.

Development opportunities

The development of local residents is prioritized. Individuals are urged to improve their well-being and attain their fullest potential. Programs are designed to ensure the population's ongoing social, cultural, and economic development. The community feels secure and is free to express themselves. As a result, further livelihood projects requiring the participation of individuals are implemented. Moreover, the local government conducts vocational skills training to increase the citizens' technical skills. In addition to farming, fishing, and raising livestock, the residents can engage in other economically viable industries.

Infrastructural improvement

The enhancement of tourist destinations is given high priority. The local government supports local enterprises that provide tourist accommodations, such as hotels, rooms, and houses for rent. Additionally, market structures are upgraded to promote local products. In connection, new concrete roads are constructed. Electricity becomes more

accessible, and safe potable water is distributed to all homes. There are health centers in every barangay, making them widely accessible to the populace.

Social upliftment

People's sense of autonomy and self-assurance were fostered. Youth engagement in sports, sociocultural activities, and other initiatives that helped them to cope with conflict-related stress were prioritized. Children once again can play, attend school on a regular basis, and pursue their aspirations in a friendly and peaceful community. Also, programs were developed to ensure that war victims can process their trauma. Those who had sustained injuries received proper medical care funded by the local government.

Improved quality of life

People can develop their business or means of livelihood without fear of coercion. Every family can raise their children in a tranquil and sustainable environment. The children are assisted mostly in their academic endeavors wherein all levels have access to various scholarships. Local community are being promoted, giving the people a sense of pride and trust towards their locality.

Reversed impression on locality's situation

The perception of the peace and order condition in the community changed from unfavorable to good. The promotion of economic, social, and cultural factors is strengthened. Members of the municipal government are performing their responsibilities effectively. Local residents regained trust in the government, resulting in increased participation in local initiatives. In addition, tourism helps individuals feel more at ease in their environment, resulting in a rise in community pride. Other surrounding municipalities initiate collaborative development. The reputation of the local business attracts several outside investments.

Agricultural development

Farmers have access to training and other initiatives that increase and broaden their knowledge of agricultural methods. Local farmers are provided with current and suitable equipment to assist them in producing high-quality goods. In addition, alternate means of subsistence were provided. These livelihoods liberate farmers, fishers, and livestock growers from dependence on their principal source of income, empowering them to be innovative with what they have and what they can do.

Enhanced government structure

The government officials were provided with sufficient training to strengthen their administrative skills and understanding. The welfare of the local community is the highest concern. Any threats of conflict are strictly monitored and given proper attention. Moreover, people were encouraged to communicate their views without fear of intimidation from government officials. Importantly, government officials practice

transparency, the people were given proper and factual information about the local condition.

Enhanced peaceful negotiations

The intensity of promoting negotiation towards peaceful settlement was actualized. The initiative conducted by the LGU to the militant to stop the emerging problems to the community had finally been achieved. The community had to promote the task force in mobilizing their security control over their premises. The community itself had developed strategies and policy in preventing the coming of militants. Moreover, there was help offered by the LGU like training to BPAT officers of the baranggay. Also, the appearance of military battalion manifested strong security assets.

Absence of Conflict

The community lives in harmony where opportunities were available without the fear of conflict. For instance, \ members were able to pursue their livelihoods, the children were going to school and play, and the government officials were continuously supporting and securing the people and the whole place from any threat of conflict.

Economic Process of Transition from Conflict to Peace

There were identified aspects of economic processes from the respondents like perception of economic means towards peace, economic condition during conflict, and perceived effects of transition process to development of peace. Over the past years, the conflicted areas were able to transform their areas into resourceful and abundant locality where peace talks, and agreements had neutralized economic conditions. Furthermore, the community was responsive to economic mobility from stakeholders and government agencies where it improved their engagement into production and sales due to emerging context of tourism as evidence of peaceful locality.

B1. Perception on Economic Means Towards Peace

The highlights of these economic means towards peace were identified as a form of government support through livelihood programs, security, and mental wellness.

Table 6: Perception on Economic Means toward Peace

Themes	Description
Government support	When the LGU funds for the economic stability of the community. Ready-to-respond government services. When there is strong support from local and national relief programs.
Livelihood	When programs like livestock and farming materials are provided. When the community have sources of income

	and food. When residents have permanent jobs and stable or regular earnings.
Security	Secured visibility area. When they can do business without threats from NPAs. When the locality is conflict free.
Mental wellness	When people are mentally focused towards attaining good lives.

Government Support through Livelihood Programs

The first initiator to support and serve the community in times of conflict was headed by LGU or government in general. The government support through livelihood programs comes as lifesaving helps to assist the community from conflicted areas. According to the participants, the government did not miss anything and offered relevant services to them. As strong evidence, health and wellness were also prioritized.

Security

The participants believed that security is a mean why do people from neighboring localities visited their areas. The attendance of visitors of coming in was observed because of the enforced mode of security to the areas. Since there is a visible checkpoint of PNP, the BPAT also reinforced this means where visitors can move without any hesitation about their safety.

Mental wellness

Mental wellness is also important according to the participants. They believed mental health is a strong foundation to uplift their mental conditions such as fear and violence from the past years. Good mental health means that they can focus and persevere to their dreams and aspirations while facing the challenges in our society. Part of assisting the health condition of the community, the youth were encouraged to participate because of the prior traumas they suffered from

B2. Economic Situation During Conflicts

These problems cause a decrease in productivity, trade, and investment. Both LGU and community strived to prioritize safety over jobs and production since some relocated to conflict-free locality. This resulted in emerging problems to settlement and displacement. There was strong behavior of community to rely to government aid, rely to farm produce, limited agriculture, limited income, and fear. It was believed that progress and development in economic conditions were difficult to attain.

Table 7: Economic Situation during Conflicts

Themes	Description
Reliance to government aid	People relied upon government services and programs.
Reliance to farm produce	People generally rely on their crops harvested.
Limited agriculture	Planting, harvesting, and livestock activities are limited. Farmlands were not cultivated because security was not stable. Roads are not conducive for transportation of farm produce. Livelihood assistance was decreased.
Limited income	People have limited, problematic, and unstable sources of income.
Fear	People are afraid. Entrepreneurs are afraid to invest in business as they receive death threats, and some get killed. Some were threatened by the presence of the NPA. They were afraid to be ambushed.

Reliance on government aid

The community relied on the availability of government aid. For the participants, the unpredicted causes of conflict turn down the mobility of the community for farming and improving their resources. Security, economic, and livelihood aids were made available for the community to be used as stepping hope in coping with conflict. It was true enough, according to the participants, that their situation cannot be described. Every day was a busy day. LGUs and NGOs were the bread and butter of the community.

Reliance to farm produce

Farming has become the primary source of economic income for the community. The participants enumerated that corn, palay, and banana (cardava) were abundantly produced in their areas. Aside from it, livestock were another alternative source of income for the residents in different barangays. The locality is popular to produce large amount of farm products in the region. Farmers were also updated on the new technologies in agricultural and livestock production.

Limited agriculture

There were limited planting activities observed for many years. This failure of the agriculture sector was caused by prevailing incidents of ambush, killings, and hold up. The residents were convinced to wait for proper time when combatant group moved to other areas. Farmers left their land field idle and caused production in the entire locality to be few. For the participants, the LGU and DA strived to introduce economic support and binding negotiations with other groups. The presence of security forces helped to at least minimize prevailing violence.

Limited income

In the geographical setting of the community, farming is a common source of income. But this led to a limited income because of the occurring issues to security and peace. When the situation was triggered, the participants stopped and stayed at home for their safety. The coming months harvested crops had little to produce since unstable peace also affected their economic income. These how did the participants tell their story caused by conflict to their area.

Fear

Fear caused the community to minimize their movements. This led to limited activities in entrepreneurial and development of the community. Tantamount to threats and ambushed, the participants cannot even decide what to pursue since they prioritized their safety. The situation was triggered when a member of their community was ambushed due to non-compliance with the demands of NPA. In the height of this situation, the intervention of military forces becomes their savior.

B3. Economic Means and Interventions to Cope from Conflicts

A. Economic Means

The community looked at these economic means as tools to overcome the problems and prevailing issues of fear. From the participants' perspective, these means worked to boost agriculture, livelihood programs, 4Ps programs, security forces, and refraining from military alliances. Through these activities, the community was able to overcome and still stand from these challenges.

Table 8: Economic Means to Cope from Conflicts

Themes	Description
Agricultural Boost	LGU led programs on high value crops, implemented agricultural programs, provided livestock, and cash assistance for agriculture.
Livelihood programs	DSWD and DA implemented livelihood programs and skills. Support from NGOs was prioritized.
4Ps Program	DSWD provided monetary assistance to the deserving poor families.
Security force	The people looked upon the armed Philippine armed force and the LGU for security. The security force conduct monitoring.
Refraining from military alliances	The residents refrained from joining armed movements.

Agricultural Boost

The local government unit's agricultural programs are equipped with the vision of helping the local farmers to cope with conflict related problems. These programs aimed to help the local farmers produce a high value crop, livestock and with cash assistance. It ensures that no local farmers will be left behind. The support of DA in boosting agriculture took place.

Livelihood programs

The DSWD and DA ensured that numerous livelihood programs will be given to assist their effective recovery. For instance, the women were taught with various skills focused in converting local items into market ready products. It also aims to teach and assist the local residents not to be dependent on a single source of income, rather through creativity and resourcefulness, the local residents can create numerous means of income.

4Ps Program

The Pantawid Pamilyang Pilipino Program is a human development measure of the government that provides cash grants to the deserving poor residents in order to facilitate their health, nutrition, and the education of the children. In the case of the affected local residents, 4Ps cash assistance is a big relief. The cash grants are divided into two; the health grant and education grant.

Security force

In terms of security, the Philippine Armed Forces, the local police and LGU personnel ensure that conflict and its possible emergence are always checked and taken under control. The emergence of lawlessness and crimes are taken as top priority concern. The people start to feel safe again. The local community and LGU are coming together to establish a better and peaceful community.

Refraining from military alliances

The local residents ensured that participations in various armed and rebel groups are greatly discouraged. They chose to live in harmony with each other. For instance, the local government encourages the people to report any suspicion at the same time, peaceful surrendering of guns and other ammunition possessed by the former members of armed movements are administered.

B. Economic Interventions

The so-called economic interventions posted improvement and facilitated the welfare of the community. This brought an increase of skills and alleviated life-long support to their family. The participants remembered how the help from different stakeholders and government agencies assisted them from the day one of occurrence of conflict up to stability of the situation. The active interventions can be summarized into

skills training, recovery programs and strategies, economic determinism, limited farming, limited entrepreneurship, economizing, and security force.

Table 9: Economic Interventions to Cope from Conflicts

Themes	Description
Alternative income sources developed	People have alternative income sources and consequently food provisions. New businesses and new jobs were developed.
Infrastructural development	The community were able to build their new homes. Barangay roads were concreted making them conducive for economic activities.
Regained livelihood	Livelihood activities regained their forms. The community engaged in businesses. Farmers regained interest in farming and fishing. They started to invest in business and farming.
Minimized conflict	Minimized number of recorded conflicts. The number of threats and conflict incidences were lessened. The people were safeguarded from the NPA.
Dependence upon aid	The community waited for more donations to come from different sectors.
Empowerment	Women were now able to work. Religious organizations stood up to protect their members.
Educational recovery	Children are now able to go to school.
Subsistence	They were able to eat at least 3 times a day. The interventions at least lessened the community's burden. The people were able to earn income at even the least amount.

Skills trainings

The local government unit and in partnership with other government agencies offer various trainings that could help the local residents learn and develop various skills. For instance, the Department of Trade and Industry conducts programs like Negosyo Centers, Kapatid Mentor me and Small and Medium Enterprise Roving Academy. These programs envision to create more jobs and livelihoods by aiding the boost of the growth

of local enterprise. The DTI assists the local business in making proper branding, processing, and manufacturing of their products.

Recovery programs and strategies

The Department of Agriculture provides not just livelihood programs but also conducts certain strategies that can assist the local workers go back to their former jobs. For instance, some of the local buildings and other infrastructures were damage during the conflict, instead of hiring external contractors, they employ the local carpenters and laborers and at the same time help the local workers gain moral confidence towards their jobs.

Economic determinism

One of the initiatives of the local residents with the guidance coming from the local government unit, they systematized food to table planting. This program encourages the local residents to grow their own food for their own consumption. The local government unit provides seeds in various kinds. At the same time, the local government continues to conduct programs and seminars that can develop the knowledge and skills of the community.

Limited farming

One of the coping mechanisms of the local residents is to practice limited fishing and farming. This method allows the local farmers and fishermen to farm in limited manner. For instance, farmers only plant certain kind of crops that can grow without maintenance. These farmers also ensured that these plants could grow within a small period of time. For the meantime, these initiatives helped them to harvest limited production.

Limited entrepreneurship

Local business started to operate in small scales. It ensured that even in limited manner, the local business is still running. Allowing the operation of local businesses help the whole local economy to continue despite the conflict. The local government systematized the market day schedule. Instead of having daily market openings, it is minimized to only once in a week. Although in limited manner, the local business is still able to operate.

Economizing

Local businesses are gradually returning to normal. People regain their confidence in their business endeavors. The local government assisted and protected citizens' means of subsistence. The livelihood initiatives assisted people in generating sources of income. As a result, better jobs are developed for the public.

Security force

With the security assistance of the local police and other government personnel, the local business is able to thrive. Training is provided to ensure that the populace has proper business management knowledge, and if they wish to pursue business, they are supported and guided by the government. The presence of the local police is apparent in every business center, especially in public markets, seaports, and small business stalls. People can develop their business or means of livelihood without fear of coercion.

B4. Perceived Effects of Transition Process to Development of Peace

There are two perceived effects generated from the interview: positive and negative effects. These effects affect the transition process to the development of peace.

Positive Effects

In the transition process to development of peace, positive effects were experienced and turned out to be helpful to the people from disruption. The outcome of peace negotiation and agreement between GPH, MILF and some NPA members shed opportunities and normalizing the conditions that was once present. These positive effects could be summed up through alternative income resources developed, presence of infrastructure development, regained livelihood, and minimized conflict, dependency upon aid, empowerment, educational recovery, and subsistence.

Table 10: Positive Effects

Themes	Description
Skills trainings	The LGU offered skills training to the community. DTI assisted the proper branding and process of manufacturing their products.
Recovery programs and strategies	The DA implemented recovery programs for the community. A carpenter informant searched for more opportunities to construct houses and buildings to economically recover.
Economic determinism	The community practiced table food planting for their own consumption. Knowledge and skills of the community in making their products were improved.
Limited farming	Some continued fishing and farming but in small scale.
Limited entrepreneurship	Small entrepreneurs started to operate on small scales. Weekly market day is observed.
Economizing	Expenses and budgets were minimized.
Security force	Market activities were assisted by security force for safety.

Alternative income sources developed

When the community had started to return and settle permanently to their ancestral lands, the LGU offered aid services and job opportunities to them. Like for instance, small store or “Talipapa” were constructed near the newly concreted roads generated incomes to the community. Harvested crops and vegetables were sold to travelers and tourists from their farms.

Infrastructural development

A concrete road was the most likely project, which changed the travel distance of the community. In this way, the participants perceived the importance of the road as received from the government. The accessibility of the community to neighboring villages and the market shortened their time to travel. In addition, locally produced crops can arrive immediately at scale facilities. Farmers found it favorable for their businesses. People also preferred to construct their homes along highways. The community stressed out that road construction had a good favor for them.

Regained livelihood

The offshoot of transition process provided strong regain to livelihood. This was the underlying effect where the government agencies offered immediate assistance to them. Moreover, the DA empowered the farmers on their methodology and materials needs to plant crops as they were trying to improve harvests and optimal export of localized crops from their hometown. The effective shift of people to prioritize farming industry necessitates continued implementation of peace and order. As a result of this transition, LGU reported an increase in production.

Minimized conflict

The appearance of security forces and implementation of peace agreements become evident. The community had found minimal conflict sparsely reported. This was because the BLGU maximized their operation in providing checkpoint entries and policy to conflict resolution. Through this active participation of the community and military forces, there were able to control and avoid entrance and attacks of NPA to their area.

Dependence upon aid

People left homeless and other belongings. The participants believed that any forms of aid they accepted as long as it benefited their families especially shelter, medicines, livelihood, and foods. They gathered in a center where they spent days and even a month while waiting to normalize the situations. Tons of supplies arrived from different sectors who helped the victims of conflict. The United Nations and other health-supports agencies collaborated so that everyone had everything on table.

Empowerment

Women empowerment become another perspective that changed the community's thinking about women's roles and identity. Unlike before, women were limited to household chores and taking care of their children. But the appearance of women in the community opened doors of opportunities. Even in cultural and religious views about women, it showed support by developing their skills and education. The LGUs initiated programs for women particularly to economic perspectives. According to the Tourism Officer of Pikit, this is how they provided women's support to develop their entrepreneurial ability.

Educational recovery

The prevailing result of transitions process was the educational recovery of the locality from the years of informal education brought by conflict. For the participants, formal peace talks, and agreement normalize the area. They observed that there were an increasing number of children who were actively present at the school. This was because the stability of peace in the area provided accessibility for the community to engage in formal education.

Subsistence

By this, the subsistence peace offered a change to their mental wellbeing. In other words, the consistency of having good foods, generating income, and peaceful sleep at night captured an identity of life that supposed to be treated. People can do things about their plans for their children. They were lots of source of income because they can tilt their farmlands.

Negative Effects

There were two major negative effects identified by the participants on how they struggled to it: difficulty in entrepreneurship and opting to migrate.

Table 11: Negative Effects of Transition Process to Development of Peace

Themes	Description
Difficulty in entrepreneurship	The community is still having a hard time conducting regular market day.
Opting to migrate	Some people preferred to relocate to other towns.

Difficulty in entrepreneurship

By this, the participants had to be prepared for any time that conflict may happen, and they needed to travel to a safe area. The tendency of this was they cannot stay longer for their place and cannot cultivate their agricultural land fields. Moreover, their respected LGUs concentrated more on ensuring safety, providing health related services, and

conflict management deliberation with unit head while investment for infrastructure, economic response, and investment were left problematic. The scenarios that conflict produced negative effects come across to other development plans.

Opting to migrate

Another negative effect that was once an evolving situation among the areas were opting to migrate. Hundreds of people wished to end the existing conflict, but they found themselves deciding to migrate to peaceful municipalities and cities where they could find refuge from their direct family members and relatives.

Security Processes of Transition from Conflict to Peace

From peacebuilding to economics processes, security becomes a strong defense established in the locality. It brought alliance with government security forces which unanimously unveiled opportunities and resistance from possible conflict. The participation of other leading public and private agencies made ties and contracts to ensure that no more destabilizations may come. More strategies were employed to suite existing conflict. But the presence of destabilizers made a rough movement to lead into harmonious establishment of peace and order.

Perceived Causes of Destabilization of Security in the Locality

The occurrence of destabilization caused by outlawed combatants created great disappearance and struggle of the community. A few destabilizers had contact with Philippine military forces and local peacekeepers in the barangays which devastated millions of security support. The Moro private armed group, BIFF, MILF, Rido, and NPA were the identified destabilizers of the residents.

Table 12: Perceived Causes of Destabilization of Security in the Locality

Themes	Description
Moro private armed group	In conflict with Christians and Philippine government. Caused massive separations and migration to the locality. Recorded conflicts emerge in isolated areas.
Bangsamoro Islamic Freedom Fighter	Emerged to escalate the peace agreement of the government and MILF.
Moro Islamic Liberation Front	Numbers of reports killings with Philippine army.
Rido	A cultural conflict which caused fear to the residents.
New People's Army	Caused community to fear. Ambush recorded in the community

Moro Private Armed Group

This group called by the participants as Moro private armed group who become the early caused conflict to Christian villages and some remote places. According to the participants, the appearances of Moro and Christians war was due to land conflict and misunderstanding. The Moro feared Christians and vice-versa. From the Christian point of view, the Moro were tagged as traitor and untrusted individuals. While Moro perceived Christians as rubber of lands

Bangsamoro Islamic Federation Front

The breakaway group from MILF named BIFF appeared to escalate fear and violence. This destabilizer was considered as triggering group that caused tension in the community. The BLGU received reports of the coming in of the groups within their territory. The community in response were worried about what any cause that it will create to them. The possibility of conflict is likely studied. The barangay captain needed to coordinate with Purok leaders to intensify their coordination and response. The community were informed and guided of what to do in case there was conflict.

Moro Islamic Liberation Front

The participants believed that violence and conflict were created by the MILF group in southern region. After the separation of MILF from MNLF group, there were an increasing recruitment. The participants had trouble to live a peaceful because of the killings and threats caused by the MILF. Recent reports of bombing were ordered by this group. The GRP prepared their troops and surveillance to the areas in Cotabato, Maguindanao, and Sultan Kudarat.

Rido

Rido is another destabilizer of regional peace. Moro's cultural conflict caused greater disruption to other audiences in the area. The extent of its influence in society also caused hurt and concern that unexpected combat will erupt anytime soon. The difficulty with this issue was that the community where members live became victims, making their security a concern. For the participants, this is what it feels like when there is Rido.

New People's Army

The participants regarded the presence of NPA as a destabilizer in their community. The community will be charged a revolutionary tax. The community's failure to supply their insistent amount resulted in the ambush of its members. As a result of this incident, there is a limitation in mobility and progress. The participants mentioned how they faced the difficulty with NPA in their area.

Agents of and Actions towards Maintaining Security

To further initiate maintenance of security to the locality, the agents of security established groups and made alliances to personnel both in local and national security forces, to cater emergency response needs to the community who suffered from a draining pond of hope for peace. There were responsive authorities in active status ready to engage once any conflict might come. Agents of security were identified to facilitate the ongoing settlement and negotiations with the combatants. Always in the lists were the LGU, BPAT, CAFGU, PNP, AFP, Barangay Captain, Mayor, Governor, and community locals. They served to fully secure the areas and reports incidents related to peace and security of the community.

Table 13: Agents and Actions towards Maintaining Security

Themes	Description
Local Government Unit	Communicated with the national government on security issues. Properly checked tourists coming in and going out from the locality.
Barangay Peacemaking	Provided training on security. Developed strong collaboration with other security forces.
Citizen Armed Forces Geographical Unit	Established firmness and stability.
Philippine National Police	Visibility in the tourism area.
Armed Forces of the Philippines	Established detachment facility.
Barangay Captain	Established a brigade within the barangay. Conducted constant coordination with local officials. Prohibited direct contact between outsiders and residents of the locality.
Mayor	Led and collaborated with BLGU and stakeholders. Contacted with rebel groups and offered helped to eliminate the existing conflict in the locality
Governor	Provided projects to BLGU in terms of livelihood and security force. Forged peaceful aid to the community
Community locals	Initiated installation of CCTV cameras. Tourism sites assigned security forces. Conducted daily regular monitoring.

Local Government Unit

The leading organization who is very active to provide basic needs of the community is the LGU. The participants considered the direct service and response provided by this office. Their immediate needs were given in particular to those who were in conflict situation in form of shelter, food, and transport. These needs were not limited, only to these. There were DSWD, DoT, DTI, and MDRRM projects to improve the life-conditions

and wellbeing of the community. In the management level, the negotiation process, commitment of national government to security issues and implementation of projects remained the top priority of LGU.

Barangay Peacemaking Action Team

BPAT played vital roles in the promotion of safety to the residents. According to the participants, the community-based security was orderly responsible to offer a relevant establishment of monitoring. Its main agenda was to make the environment free from invasions and identify the root cause of destabilizers. They were enforced with capacitated skills and knowledge in securing the community. Their orders were supervised by their barangay captain. For the participants, this is how BPAT maintained the order of the community.

Citizen Armed Forces Geographical Unit

The CAFGU was named as protector of the ongoing conflict and even after it was solved. This military force remained vigilant and untiring clear the areas with the presence of combatants. They are more likely guarded within the border lines of the local communities for stability. The damage caused by combatants made the community seek assistance from them.

Philippine National Police

The PNP intensified their operations to combat destabilizers and maintained security to the locals and the visitors as well. In light of conflict, the exclusive purpose of PNP will always do with regular checking of the behaviors of the community and monitors the entrance in the city.

Armed Forces of the Philippines

The national government mandated the AFP to collaborate with them especially in the call for massive sustainability of security to the community. Most cases that AFP took into were emerging in the vicinity of the combatants. In raid, surveillance and other operations, the AFP were outmost faced the critical responsibility. They appeared in critical situations. They functioned with PNP and BPAT. For the participants, the presence of AFP created a stronger presence of security.

Barangay Captain

The barangay captain managed local service to the community. They took partnership with LGU, AFP, PNP and community. As the mandate of his responsibility took effect, he was assigned the BPAT for security and developed strategies and surveillance with community. Monitors the coming in of the locals and coordinates with local officials about planning and development agenda. This parameter of responsibility created direction for the community.

Mayor

The next higher rank official under the LGU is the mayor. The concerns of the different barangays were capsulized including the variety of existing problems. In case conflict broke out, the mayor ensured all barangays were monitored. For the upliftment of situation, the mayor promoted projects and plans for local development like jobs and other economic earning. There is a creation of job opportunities and coordination with department to smoothly implement it.

Governor

The provincial administration took the larger relationship with municipalities. The priority of the governor is aiding in security. Sponsored projects to BLGU are exercised. The governor maintained that the flow of services and projects remained elusive. For the participant, the governor extended her effort.

Community locals

For security purposes, the community had to initiate a well-directed strategy to ease the problem with security. According to the participants, the community must be responsive to the BLGU and government. They must cooperate with the local leaders and report existing problems encountered with LGU.

Community Participation in Maintaining Security

In the midst of security maintenance, couples of participations arise to further improve network of supports. Inter-participation of the community was once a prevailing component in addressing problems. According to the participants, the call for security force does not depend only on military forces but a presence of community per se. Since the community can identify the root cause of existing problems, it is the community that can control and defend from outsiders. The prevailing conditions regarding community participation in security can be done through practicing vigilance, peaceful co-existence with neighbors, support system, and responsiveness.

Table 14: Community Participation in Maintaining Security

Themes	Description
Vigilance	They are vigilant to the situation. Reported conflict cases that arise in the immediate community. Avoided communicating with outsiders. Monitored the arrival of visitors. Restricted individuals who don't belong to the religious sect. Use of communication devices to promptly contact security forces.
Peaceful coexistence	Christians and Moro established good relationship. Coordination with local officials.
Support systems	Conducted meetings to develop support systems.

Responsiveness	The community followed the policies and mandates of the BLGU and LGU. The community leader followed the government's security plans. The residents remained responsive to the government and local policies. Curfew hours were followed.
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Vigilance

The ability to refrain from anybody without prior knowledge can be a practical action. The notorious identify so far engraved fear and toxicity. To avoid, it can result in feeling secure. In the community for instance, the entry of outsiders was limited. The restriction of accessibility to the members of the community without approval of the leaders or parents can minimize creating conflict. Like the practice of the participants in New Israel, they refrained from accepting visitors without approval or undergone checking.

Peaceful coexistence

By this, the participants recognized the importance of non-harming because they believed that conflict has no place in their life. The importance of good relationships in the community was highlighted. Both lived in peace and harmony, working together for everyone's benefit. This was how the participants treated one another.

Support systems

To intensify the support systems in the barangay and the community, the BLGU spearheaded the meetings through Barangay Peace and Order Council. In such a way that updated information was properly disseminated by the concerned individuals. For the participants, part of the meeting was to inform the community who to contact in time of emergency. The BPAT in the barangay can be called. But, in case the situation can no longer handle, the CAFGU and PNP were prepared to support.

Responsiveness

Security policies become a good response of the community to adopt. The participants used this to collaborate with local officials on the adoption of laws. The efficient coordination and involvement of the locals was made possible by their active response to security. Many looked for the objective since they needed to limit their nighttime movements. Curfew hours were implemented. The BPAT patrolled over the communities.

Problems Encountered in Maintaining Security

The participants identified problems they encountered. These problems are referred to as persistence of pocket conflict, insufficient police power, and infiltration of outsiders, lack of security assistance, and lack of participation in the peace process. As the result, the participants had low interest to stay rather decided to evacuate their homes while they

struggled to attain peaceful life. These problems jeopardized the value of human security and economic prosperity.

Table 15: Problems Encountered in Maintaining Security

Themes	Description
Persistence of pocket conflicts	Conflicts still exist but now in a moderate level.
Insufficient police power	The number of police force is disproportionate with the number of cases in the community.
Infiltration of outsiders	Tourists come not for tourist activities but for dating purposes. Outsiders commonly create conflict in the community.

Persistence of pocket conflicts

When peace security is not yet structured, persistence of pocket conflicts become an existence behavior. The presence of MILF, NPA and MNLF caused the alarms and disturbances. Reports in media about military targeted the location and casualties, and deaths were results of pocket conflicts that were a protest for decades already. The participants were confused about their lands that no longer a promising instead a struggle to live. According to the participants, these pocketed conflicts emerged earlier.

Insufficient police power

Police power is necessary to establish security and implement wellbeing of the community. But the number of them was not sufficient to take on the tasks. The problem with the implementation was also caused by minimal police officer to monitor and conduct surveillance. The participants were worried about their security status. The uneven distribution of the security forces in managing community’s welfare meant limiting the holistic protection.

Infiltration of outsiders

The arrival of visitors from different localities can be caused by violence if there was no proper checking done. For the participants, infiltration of outsiders meant avoidance of the presence of notorious individuals. Since the emerging tourism activities become a new social gather tourism and invitation for the visitors to experience the atmosphere of tourism industry. Reports from the region highlighted the trends of tourism attractions. The DoT, however, intensified some of security measures and good conditions for the arrival of tourists. Both LGU and BLGU coordinated with DoT to ensure that everyone was enjoying themselves while in the area. This claim was also observed in the Makilala where the community monitored the entry of visitors who directly emerged in the community.

Perceived Effects of Process in Maintaining Security

While security is enforced, there are circumstances that peace will be rationalized. It can be said that in the long process of initiating inputs and activities about security, positive results are observable by the participants. LGUs and NGOs combined their resources to create a sound policy and practice for the community to maintain security matters. The effects of the processes to maintain security come in the form of safety, a sense of tranquility, economic upliftment, and tourism promotion, establishment of peace initiators, minimized conflict, and normalized community dynamics.

Table 16: Perceived Effects of Process in Maintaining Security

Themes	Description
Safety	Every family became safe because of BPAT and Tanod in the barangay. People can now go out of the community even without security support from CAFGU. Absence of fear and threats.
Sense of tranquility	The residents feel a sense of tranquility in the barangay. They feel comfortable with the present situation. The community can sleep peacefully. The people can now freely return to their homes. They feel secured wherever they go.
Economic upliftment	Businesses in tourism sites are now encouraged. People can do business calmly. Improved quality of life.
Tourism is promoted	The tourists are no longer afraid to visit Pikit and Aleosan. Number of tourists increased.
Establishment of peace initiators	Peace initiators are established in the tourism sites and the barangay.
Minimized conflict	Coercion and number of killings are now minimized.
Normalized community dynamics	Regular activities can now be done. Transactions in the community are now normalized.

Safety

Many had decided to prioritize the safety of their family that made to decide to migrate and left their belongings. Since conflict is destructive and nothing to be earned. The participants experienced long occurrences of devastating war claimed thousands of lives and resulted in massive danger to them. Safety becomes the top priority of the government agencies both in public and in private organizations. The coordination of community leaders to LGUs made changes to the behaviors and their activities. In their barangay level, the BPAT maximized their precise supervision, monitoring, and entry points of the visitors.

Sense of tranquility

When safety appeared, the behavioral characters of the community experienced a sense of tranquility. The participants were now able to sleep peacefully at night and nothing to worry about. They were content to stay and walk within their community because everything was in order. Aside from that, the comfortability to manage their plans for their family is now attainable.

Economic upliftment

The existing behavior of economic upliftment to their areas opened doors for the community to invest in business and other entrepreneurial activities to earn income. The appearance of investors and infrastructures raises awareness of the community to engage in local scale of profitable products. The return of farming activities also yields good feedback and demands for the best output of farming and business activities.

Tourism is promoted

The community and LGU had stronger bound to achieve tourism investment. The conflict-affected areas before and the mountainous land filled with grass and tress had transformed into amusement hubs for the residents and the tourists. Due to this information, the LGU made improvements to the areas and built recreational facilities while tourists enjoyed an eye-catching view. Private owners, on the other hand, also used these as opportunities to invest in tourism. The participants could not imagine how tourism provided them with a glimpse of opportunities. It changed their lives' perspectives on what they can compare to a long time ago.

Establishment of peace initiators

By this, the participants needed to strategize the tourist coming into the area. Part of the plan is the posting of registration and identification for visitors. In Makilala, for instance, the BPAT was situated in the entrance where it required visitors to log in their personal details as part of their policy agenda. Even there is enough security forced present. The DoT, through the support from LGU had forged an agreement with PNP to provide personnel to take position in the area called Tourist Police. Their responsibility is to check the situation and prepare.

Minimized conflict

The presence and enforcement of security forces, peace initiators, and government agencies minimized the occurrence of conflict. This is because the stakeholders and community had maintained their efforts to supervise the entry points of the visitors. The participation of each group made a sound outcome of imposing security mandates. Zero or no cases of conflict reported for the past years. The community believed that they could experience conflict less in society if they kept on refraining from getting involved in it. The police and security forces were on the watch position. They monitored the movements

and activities of the community. The street-roads were lit to clearly provide vision of the road and other locations. The absence of conflict resulted in a positive response from the participants.

Normalized community dynamics

It is normal again, the description for the participants in defining the status of their community. Social activities were now regularly celebrated by the participants. The community itself justified how happy they are to promote and implement their programs. It gave them a realization to call realization of the programs. More infrastructures and physical development were visible. Funding agencies were taking as a form of support and improvement to the community.

DISCUSSION

This section discusses the processes of transition from conflict to peace. Fontana, G., Siewert, M., & Yakinthou, C. (2020) in *Managing War-to-Peace Transitions after Intra-State Conflicts: Configurations of Successful Peace Processes* upholds that peace negotiation has high tendency of success and achievement for peace. These processes convene with varied agencies and stakeholders to directly surpass worsening effects of conflict. The roots of legitimacy, civilian support base and structures of governance, comprising prototypical state functions, were germinated during conflict itself (Özdem & Podder, 2012). The GRP initiates already various negotiations with rebels' groups. The first declaration of ceasefire dates back to the 1976 Tripoli Agreement and involved the MNLF (Åkebo, 2020) but failed to follow the agreement. Consistent moves to contest peace negotiation taken place in 1986, as part of the first formal peace talks under the Corazon Aquino presidency with another rebel group, the NPA. In the Presidency of Fidel Ramos, the GRP and the MILF peace panel signed a ceasefire agreement in 1997 as a starting point for engaging in peace negotiations (Åkebo, 2020). The next process formally enacted the peace agreement among Moro private armed group (MILF and MNLF) making the BARMM as the official government.

In 2014, the Comprehensive Agreement on the Bangsamoro (CAB) constituted the decommissioning and rehabilitation of MILF and later with MNLF combatants, socio-economic development programs (Loesch, 2017) and to foster peace and honor their heritage (Ochiai, 2016). Aquino administration officiates the promising peace agreement in the national history. Sombatpoonsiri (2018) believes the progress of the Bangsamoro peace process is not due to democratic government interference. Instead, success begins with local civil society being empowered to promote resiliency and peace. However, the GRP and NPA peace negotiation still cannot be served. The next paragraphs discuss the narratives of participants on the processes of transitions with emphasis on peacebuilding, economic, and security processes.

Peacebuilding Process of Transition from Conflict to Peace

From the previous discussions, it mentions historical evidence of Mindanao conflicts and parties involved in solving it. Investigating from narratives of the participants towards peacebuilding scenarios' claims and processes, this study explores understanding the process of peacebuilding. Looking into it, peacebuilding is understood as an outside to inside processes. This means that sectorial initiatives process in service department come across to the compelling problems of the community. The support system comes from other agencies and private institutions. For instance, the UN and humanitarian agencies foster unlimited aid. Certain aid takes different form of peacebuilding initiatives. One relevant peacebuilding is *Aman ki Asha* (a desire for peace) that made impactful platform using media cooperation for people-to-people contacts and peacebuilding (Clayton, Dorussen, Böhmelt, et al., 2020; Rid, 2020). This platform subscribes to the use of media in proper dissemination of information. The essence of peacebuilding to aid conflict is therefore the consistency of supporting groups in providing needs. The outside peacebuilding initiatives process like humanitarian aid from foreign countries directly influence the support in conflict situation both natural and human made. But beyond all the support, it should not compromise the security and health of the victims.

While the sectorial initiatives offer various programs to emancipate individuals from economic and social problems. Some of these initiatives are coming from outsiders. Sectorial support offers some jobs to the community. The LGUs, NGOs, stakeholders, and the community are complementarily working to end the conflict. UN recognized women participation in peacebuilding (Shepherd, 2016). In this study, the peacebuilding initiatives delivered by these sectorial agencies resulted in economic determinism, social upliftment, agricultural development and enhanced peaceful peace negotiations. For instance, Barangay Bagolibas, in Aleosan municipality became the recipient of several peace and development interventions (Daylusan - Fiesta, 2019). This is supported by other study who believes that peacebuilding is a multifaceted task that implies commitment to establishing the military, legal, political, economic, structural, cultural and psychosocial conditions necessary to promote a culture of peace in place of a culture of violence (Lambourne & Herro, 2008). Either it is from outside or inside processes domain, the goal is focused to what best can give to individuals.

Contrary to what many believe, peace initiatives transformation should be a normal state of responding to needs because of inequality, threats, and negative views about conflicts. This claim is supported by Clayton, Dorussen, & Böhmelt (2020) emphasize that peace initiatives do not always take place during times of conflict, nor are they always directly tied to a conflict. In other words, peacebuilding is concerned with more than just conflict resolution as revealed in this study. The core of peacebuilding is a continual reaction to all persons who, in some way, require assistance.

Moreover, peacebuilding initiates draw mismatching of supports. This claim is supported by the studies of Hancock (2017); Leeuwen et al., (2019) which questions peacebuilding as it envisioned and practiced by international actors. It is largely ineffective in achieving its goals of sustainable peace because at some points their support is not in harmony with the local needs. The processes from outside to inside causes unreliability of peacebuilding supports when it lacks connection. Hancock and Leeuwen et al., (2019)

found mismatching service aids and involvement from international actors to the grounds. It is suggested the necessity for locals must be involved in both the formulation and execution of peacebuilding initiatives, as well as internationals, particularly donors, must ensure that their resources are used properly (Hancock, 2017). Part of understanding the peacebuilding process is to look for inside and outside donors to match the needs and wants of people in conflicts.

Economic Process of Transition from Conflict to Peace

The participants believe that the economic process is explained through an interdependency of the community to foreign and local donors. What does it mean? The economic process prevails over existing poverty, displacement, and malnutrition of children because of the presence of destabilizers. The community has nothing to do with security that resulted in the hindrance of economic mobility and entrepreneurial marketing. Due to its presence and conditions, the communities rely only on the existing aid or donors from outside to inside.

The economic situation during conflicts can be drawn from various reasons. It has been posted by Franco (2019) that conflict in Mindanao is due to economics than to interethnic differences. Related issues with the economy during that time are the dependency of the community on government programs since security was also challenged, and people opted to migrate. The cost of living of the community depends on farming. The farmland was left uncultivated because of the escalated conflicts preventing them. Daguino & Gomez (2010) agreed that even going to their farms was also difficult as the military personnel had marked off some areas where the rebels were still reportedly hiding. The effects of conflict afflicting daily life are dealt with (Byrne & Road, 2014). International and national organizations (government) assist and offer livelihood aid. The dependency of the community is the scenario happening. Most of the community is waiting for the piles of food supply and medicine. The larger agencies also contributed to increasing aid support. However, the negative effect is that governmental funders may have felt pressure to spread the wealth to other organizations (Hancock, 2017). The government feels the pressures while their services are needed.

About initiatives made in the previous discussions, economic means to cope with conflict exist as a support system to the problem. The problem is addressing and carrying out agricultural programs and livelihood support. However, security forces are in place to help carry out the initiatives. Therefore, economic movements adhere to the security standards as measures to properly realize it. This study is supported by Cagoco-Guam (2015), where Aleosan received agricultural-based income-generating projects. These livelihood programs aim to support women's advocacy through GREAT Women as they envision the training skills needed.

While interventions to cope with conflicts are in place. Common to the participants' responses can be drawn as a form of skills training, economic, and security enforcement. It is supported by Adriano & Parks (2013), who define that the beneficiaries generally recognized the political agendas behind aids. In conflict, the community seeks support from corporate agencies like LGUs and stakeholders to satisfy their needs. To advance the recovery programs and strategies of intervention in the transition, Loesch (2017b) supports early results of the 'Bangsamoro ADVANCE program, and the 'Farmers

Advance program permitted the realization of livelihood, infrastructure, and Alternative Learning System projects, including the provision of agricultural equipment and materials, as well as capacity-building workshops.

The negative effects of the transition process portray how the economy struggles when there is conflict. It is cited by Daylusan - Fiesta (2019), who confirms that economic sources were greatly affected because of prevailing situations. As for its effects on the development of peace, there are two effects (positive and negative) generated by the participants. One of the effects is the empowerment of the locals. It is supported by Krafft (2008), as cited by Woon (2017), who mentions that mobilizing resources brings about empowerment, particularly to children who greatly suffer. The educational closure due to conflicts limits children's attendance at school, and disruptions continue for years. Children can improve their learning when the GRP and LGUs necessitate the restoration of regional peace. In addition, the regained livelihood positively offers income resources and stability to the community. This result is supported by South & Joll (2016), who believe that civilians can travel more freely, and livelihoods have begun to improve through better access to fields for planting crops. It is because conflicts have been minimized. However, the military forces keep on eyeing the territory. These positive effects contributed to the transition of the development of peace. The participants are excited to embrace the locality without terror and brutality.

There are two identified negative effects of transition, which keep challenging the entrepreneurial and migration of the community. In relation to declining support, it lies in the fact that there are few economic incentives for participation (Özerdem & Podder, 2012). It is evident in the community who prefer to relocate their family to a peaceful and secure place. More so, the economic aspect is problematic, leading to difficulty in entrepreneurial activities. That is why businesses and economic resources are stopped, not because the community refuses to make it; instead, conflicts prevent them from doing so. It is the situation that burdens the commitment of the locals to pursue income and resource development projects.

Conversely, the political agenda tries to mitigate wars among disputants and scattered threats. Woon (2017) seriously calls economic poverty the main reason for the intrusion of violence into the everyday lives of Mindanaoans. The LGUs and stakeholders benevolently take action to promote the community's welfare, but the economic effects of conflict hamper the realizability of entrepreneurial activities.

To further improve the economy (micro and macro levels) concentration of the agencies is to install economic-friendly movements which support the locals' interests. This result is supported by Capuno (2020) states that all economic activities to cope with conflicts have been enacted by GRP, which adopted several interventions and strategies. As a result, visible social, economic, and security changes have been established. Hoping the economic state of the people will be able to satisfy and normalize poverty and conflicts.

Security Process of Transition from Conflict to Peace

Human security captures the ability of the community to overcome serious misfortune due to the unpredicted occurrence of conflicts. The perceived causes of destabilization of security in the locality cause destabilization agents, actors of peace,

community participation, the problems behind the transition, and the effects of the process in maintaining security. As mentioned in the previous discussion, the province experiences varied parties involved in conflicts. Here, the destabilizers are actively situated in different municipalities but have the same purpose, to inflict violence and conflicts. The CPP-NPA-NDF causes fear and violence in the community of Makilala. This result is supported by Åkebo (2020), whose NPA has remained strong in some areas and financially resilient through domestic funding sources, including revolutionary tax. The participants also experienced being ambushed and suffered from threats.

The BIFF remains visible in Aleosan and some parts of Maguindanao and Sultan Kudarat. This result is supported by Pabotoy (2021), how extremist groups are populated in the region. Cagoco- Guiam (2015) also supports this claim and remembers in Midsayap and Aleosan November 2014 BIFF incidents. Conflagration happens in several villages and counts as displacement and burning of houses. While the MILF also appears in several places causing conflicts and disability. However, Ilagan (2014) describes MILF as principled and fair because the group honors and values the agreement to GRP- AFP. Among the combatants in the province, the MILF is only loyal and accommodated to the request and meetings with the government for peace talks and settlements. It is evident in the Bangsamoro government's peace process and the national government settlement and reconciliation program today. A cultural dispute among Muslims, Rido, exists in the province. Cagoco- Guiam (2015) supports this finding about rido in November 2014 at Kidapawan, North Cotabato, where three were killed in a family clash. These destabilizers make Cotabato province conflict-affected areas.

The transition towards security development is only possible with the agents and actors behind it. It has been presented from the previous discussions about the initiatives given by agents and actors who maintain security. The inter-agency security forces are always on the front desk to counterattack troupes that will infuse conflicts. Ilagan (2014) describes actors involved in a multi-stakeholder convergence on the peace agenda bonded the various actors to improve the people's capacity to initiate, sustain, and manage communal peace. Through these agendas, the commitment and realizability of security are used to impart safety to the community.

Also, Berhe (2017) states that local administrations are tasked to maintain peace and stability, which includes running peace and reconciliation meetings, ensuring the collection of small arms in their communities, and reintegrating soldiers returning to their areas. The LGUs are first to investigate and monitor the situation. After that, mediation takes place as congruent with the proper process.

Community participation in maintaining security appears as an additional support system. The strong perseverance of the community's involvement in improving security activities is certainly motivated to ensure everyone's wellness. In human security, local leaders can craft their perspective and apply it to specific areas. For instance, the peace zone in Sagada, a tourist destination, underscores the importance of acknowledging civilian communities as sovereign actors existing within and in parallel to the sovereignty of two competing actors, the Philippine government and CPP-NPA-NDF (Macaspac & Peoples, 2018). The empowerment of civilian authority to maintain, negotiate and decide on existing issues made them provide solutions solely. However, in the case of Cotabato community security, the participants are persistent enough to practice vigilance. Any misbehavior expressed in society should be reported to authorities like the BPAT. The

Makilala tourism spot also offers this scenario of updating and reporting events related to security. Even though the appearance of BPAT is strong enough to inject security, the community is directed to refrain from any anomalies that may disrupt peace occasions and harmony.

The problems encountered in maintaining security become the struggle of the community. The main purpose of the GRP is to slow down the frequent conflicts erupting in various identified areas. However, security maintenance is not only focused on MILF. Instead, pocketed conflicts are caused by other troops and organizations. It has been supported by Åkebo (2020) that the conflict landscape in Mindanao is complex, with multiple armed elements and sources of violence. By this, the attention of the government to pacify numerous conflicted organizations is scattered and loses concentration. Because of the appearance of BIFF, ISIS, and NPA in areas, the government has to double or triple its preparations. It means more money and military forces resources are spent on preventing conflicts.

The participants also believed that even though numerous combatants reside in different areas of Mindanao. Still, the need for security is reinforced and delivered. The full preventive measures are fully enacted. The lower local government office is intensifying efforts to end the possible security problem.

The establishment of security agents and actors towards maintaining security from conflict to peace shows positive effects when it comes to opportunities and development of the community. Safety measures are observed as part of the perception of the participants. The access to and why people come suggest the stability of security is present. Part of the measure is the presence of security forces on highways. It is supported by Ilagan's (2014) security forces' presence along the highway to immediately investigate and report emerging safety and security concerns. The PNP posts checkpoints for entry and conducts inspections of the individuals traveling. It leads to local monitoring of BPAT officers in their tourism sites. This establishment of peace initiators helps to increase the economic activities of the locals. The national support through PNP, CAFGU, and other military forces remains evident to control and supply security aid to the community, more likely with the presence of tourism sites.

Aside from the stability of security and establishment of peace initiators, the sense of tranquility is believed to be the persistent behavior within the community. The absence of local conflicts creates a mode of tolerance of free movements and conduct of social interactions. It allows the minimization the conflicts. Dilts et al. (2012) insist tranquility (often if not always mistaken for peace) masks deeper and more pervasive violence. For many reasons, the establishment of security in tourist spots and villages where security forces dominate and offer conforming situations. In the community's mind, it is exciting to move without worries. Physical and social conveniences are more sensible to do than before.

Another effect that leads to peace and security is economic upliftment. The economic sound that security can create becomes the new trend in the community with the introduction of the tourism industry. The success of security opens gates to more economic activity for the locals, especially those who live in the areas where tourism is mushrooming. Job opportunities are created, and the transformation of barren lands becomes the center of economic activities for the community. Manalo (2017) believes tourism contributes to the local economy and the nation. He describes the effects of

tourism providing benefits and economic income for the development of the community around it and for the country as a whole.

The local community, like women, can now stand for their economic independency aside from being a mother. The initiatives provided by government agencies and private sectors assume their purpose and contribution. For El-Bushra (2000), as cited in Veneracion-Rallonza (2015), deliberately defending women's newfound economic potential can backfire when men try to reclaim and reassert their position as head of the family and household. It means that women can stand alone and not be too dependent on their partners.

The promotion of tourism becomes the source of the community's income. It is supported by Ruhanen et al. (2013), who examine the promotion of tourism as a tool for indigenous people to develop their communities. The income from tourism activities through initiatives of the community to earn provides economic support to their personal and social development. Aside from these scenarios, the role of tourism is both in showcasing the region to potential new residents and providing the services and facilities (Moscardo et al., 2013). Tourists and investors see the potential for expanding their business in tourist destinations. Cotabato tourism industries try to cater to the possibility of this development because of the level of accommodation and infrastructural development; the tourism industry depends on what the provincial government can support them. The amount of support to fill based on the needs and development of the area still depends on the availability of funds to be given.

Conclusions

This study concludes that the process of transforming conflict includes peacebuilding process, economic process, and security process. It offers a variety of development, especially women empowerment as a form of social, economic, and security development. Their roles toward peace transition exhibit a horizon of and on how society accepts them. Moreover, the direction of women in economic growth testifies to their acceptability and openness to cultural indifferences and attributes. The restoration of peace reflects eliminating prejudice, building strong support systems, and welcoming cultural boundaries. In addition, upholding culture-to-culture, and people-to-people relations forge genuine peace for all.

Recommendations

This study recommends comprehensive visit to other processes involving conflict transformation and similar elements of peace actors for the sustenance of development. The government partner agencies to provide sound programs in the improvement of diverse community alliance to peacebuilding measures and collaboration; open to women livelihood and economics means to address economics gaps among the affected poor

families, and security contacts and improvement for continuous stability of peace to the entire province.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher maintained and valued the confidentiality of the participants' information. By their willingness, without any force made, they shared their experiences according to the purpose of the study. The researcher also used to inform- consent that values the participants' interest. All the data obtained during the interview was used mainly for the study. Proper referencing was also observed to credit the authors' ideas during the analysis and further discussion in the study. The researcher ensured that the rights, safety, and -being of all participants were protected throughout the research process. Informed consent was given. The participants were informed about the risks associated with their involvement in the research and given an opportunity to make a voluntary decision to participate in or not participate in the research.

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